

Reactions of IRRI strains to gall midge at Chiplima, India

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Eight advanced International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) rice strains and 64 strains of Indian origin were subjected

to a gall-midge resistance varietal trial at the Regional Research Station of Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology during 1975 and 1976 in the main crop season (May to November). The silver shoot count revealed that none of the IRRI lines had absolute resistance, but when compared with the susceptible check Jaya, each showed a certain degree of resistance (see table). ❧

Yields and silver shoot (ss) count of IRRI cultivars, 1975 and 1976 main crop seasons. Chiplima, India.

Cultivar	Ss (no./sq m)		Yield (kg/ha)	
	1975	1976	1975	1976
IR2071-621-2-3	29	0	1749	3030
IR2071-636-5-2-6	14	0	2726	2479
IR2070-414-3-9	16	28	720	3305
IR2070-439-6-5	2	25	1955	3030
IR2070-464-1-3-6	5	11	4012	2823
IR2070-471-2-5	50	0	1749	2410
IR2071-213-6-6	108	77	1235	2617
IR2071-486-9-2	13	11	3292	2823
RPW 6-13 (Resistant check)	5	56	1646	1377
Jaya (Susceptible check)	163	95	1235	413

seedlings are transplanted in July or August. Short-duration varieties are grown in the uplands and the long-duration varieties elsewhere. Tall indigenous types withstand drought stress more or less in the uplands, but are usually poor yielders; many recent high yielding varieties are drought susceptible.

A number of suitable upland rice varieties from the International Rice Upland Rice Nursery in 1976 at Bankura and Purulia were identified. Seeds of 185 types were drilled at two sites in June 1976. Twenty-five local entries were added at Bankura. Growth, effect of drought stress, and other factors were recorded periodically during frequent, prolonged periods of rainless days. About 50% of the entries were credited with acceptable tolerance for drought. Some promising types are listed in the table. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Adverse soils

Breeding for adverse-soils tolerance

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In densely populated South and Southeast Asia, 100 M ha suited to rice lie idle largely because of soil toxicities (Table 1). Also, on about 50 M ha of cultivated land, deficiencies of zinc, phosphorus, or iron, or excesses of iron, aluminum, or manganese limit rice yields.

In 1976 the International Rice Research Institute screened cultivars from its germ plasm bank, evaluated promising lines, and tested the progeny from its hybridization program for tolerance of adverse soil conditions (Table 2).

Table 1. Problem rice soils (current and potential) of South and Southeast Asia.

Kind of soil	Extent (M ha)
Saline soils	62.5
Alkali soils	2.2
Acid sulfate soils	9.8
Organic soils	29.0

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Drought tolerance

Upland rice varieties for drought-prone areas of West Bengal, India

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Rice that depends solely on rainfall occupies about 69% of the rice land in Bankura district and 86% in Purulia

district in West Bengal, India. Short and badly distributed rainfall, undulating land, and poor soil-moisture retention are chiefly responsible for frequent drought. In 1976 rice experienced its most severe drought of recent times.

Seed is usually sown with the onset of the southwest monsoon in June (monsoon lasts until September), and

Promising upland rice varieties for drought-prone areas of West Bengal, India.

Name	Source	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)
Se. 322 B.19	Senegal	91	4.44
IRAT 10	Ivory Coast	92	4.10
IET 1444	India	105	3.88
B.9c-Md-3-3	Indonesia	105	3.84
Brown Gora	India	92	3.60
DV 110	Bangladesh	106	3.50
DZ 41		91	3.48
ARC 7060	India	92	3.28
IET 3226		100	3.23
C22	IRRI	118	3.20
B.541 c/km/19/3/4	Indonesia	118	3.20
Se. 319 G.	Senegal	89	3.19
IR2035-227-1	IRRI	119	3.08
Aus 8	Bangladesh	114	3.00

Table 2. Rice cultivars screened for adverse-soil tolerance. IRRI, 1976.

Source	Rice cultivars (no.) screened for					
	Salinity	Alkalinity	Iron toxicity	Organic soils	Zinc deficiency	Phosphorus deficiency
Germ plasm bank	1446	1338	12	0	5918	1134
General breeding program	1020	2397	108	195	850	330
Specific hybrids	2059	676	0	0	0	0
Total	4525	4411	120	195	6768	1464

Four IR4630 and IR4763 lines showed high salt tolerance; IR30, IR32, IR36, and 13 advanced breeding lines had moderate tolerance. IR4227-28-3 and IR4227-104-3 revealed high tolerance for alkalinity and 52 advanced breeding lines showed moderate tolerance. IR20, IR34, BG90-2, and several elite lines tolerated zinc deficiency. IR20, IR29, IR32, and many elite lines from the crosses

IR2031, IR2070, IR2071, and IR2153 manifested tolerance for iron toxicity. IR28, IR29, IR30, IR34, IR1514A-E666, and several IR2061 lines tolerated phosphorus deficiency.

Several IR varieties and many IRRI elite lines with good agronomic characteristics and resistance to diseases and insects showed tolerance to adverse soils even though no conscious effort had been made to achieve it. ❧

of observation. The other originally healthy plants showed disease symptoms after the third or fourth week.

The studies suggest, in addition to stubble burning, the following control measures: (1) control of weeds and volunteer rice, (2) dikes and banks to prevent river overflow onto fields, and (3) clean cultivation and early roguing of diseased plants. ❧

Possible presence of bacterial blight in Latin America

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Bacterial blight had not been previously reported in America. During my visit to rice farms in Panama on 5 and 6 August 1976 and in Ecuador on 10 and 11 August, I observed some rice showing symptoms of the disease, and several weeds with similar symptoms. On 12 August I forwarded a report of my observations to the directors general of the International Center of Tropical Agriculture (CIAT) and the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI). What follows is excerpted from the report.

On a rice farm of the Bayano project of the Panama government, CR1113, a variety newly selected from an IRRI line in Costa Rica, was about to flower. Small and large patches of blighted upper leaves, similar to those seen in bacterial blight in the early stage of an epidemic, were seen near edges of the farm. Close examination revealed the characteristic symptoms of the disease. Nearby roadside colonies of a common noxious weed *Manisuris* sp. likewise showed symptoms. Bacterial blight symptoms were also found in patches on a second farm planted to CICA 6. There *Manisuris* sp. and colonies of wild rice *Oryza latifolia* were also infected, some severely. Blighted patches were found on a third farm planted to Nilo 1; nearby *Manisuris* sp. and *O. latifolia* were infected. More disease was found on a seed-multiplication farm for possible new varieties bred locally between IR8 and Nilo 1; a great deal of *Manisuris* sp. nearby was severely infected, as was a weed locally called "Cabezona." A large sage with triangular

Pest management and control DISEASES

Ufra disease spread by water flow

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In Irrawaddy Delta, Burma, ufra disease of rice caused by the nematode *Ditylenchus angustus* is associated with lowlands onto which rivers overflow because of tidal action. Field observations showed the following sources of the disease inoculum: (1) the wild rice *Oryza perennis*, growing along banks of waterways, its roots in mud and its tops above water surface; (2) *O. meyeriana*; (3) *Leersia hexandra*; and (4) volunteer rice plants.

On a healthy rice plant grown in a pot with a diseased plant, especially in open air in the rainy season, chlorotic leaves appear in 2 weeks, suggesting that water is the agent of disease spread. The following experiment showed dispersal along currents.

In a 100-m canal, 30 cm wide and 18 cm deep (see figure), water was put in and drained at the rate of about 1 liter/minute. One group of 10 C4-63 rice plants with ufra disease and four groups of healthy plants were placed in the canal at 20-m intervals.

The upstream group of plants remained healthy throughout 10 weeks

Plan of an experiment to test the transmission of ufra disease of rice through paddy water.